

Year 1 Annual Report (May 2023—Apr 2024)

Lead institution: Lancaster University

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1. A summary of the project to date, in line with success criteria

The Open Book Futures (OBF) project will initiate a step-change in the ambition, scope and impact of open access (OA) book publishing, by significantly increasing and improving the quantity, discoverability and accessibility of academic content made available freely and easily to scholars and the wider public. Work on our project is divided across 6 work packages (WP2-7), with WP1 reserved for project management. Full details of each WP's success criteria is provided in the table below. Here, we offer a summary of each WP's activities in Year 1 of the project, with reference to relevant project-wide objectives:

WP2, Open Book Collective (OBC):

The Open Book Collective (OBC) enables libraries and other institutions to financially support open access initiatives via its Supporter Programmes. The OBC was initially developed under OBF's predecessor project COPIM (2019-2023), and a key objective for the OBF project is to 'enhance the impact' of infrastructures like the OBC. In Year 1 of the OBF project, the OBC held its first Annual Assembly of Custodians, and in Dec 2023 it became a registered charity: two crucial milestones for enhancing and securing the OBC's long-term impact, mission and sustainability. Moreover, proactive outreach work has allowed the OBC to exceed its targeted revenue growth in Year 1 of the OBF project by ca. 25%, and the platform has grown to include 3 additional new publishers and 61 supporting institutions from around the world (see success criteria A2.1 and A2.5). Thanks to close consultation with publishers and other stakeholders, enhancements to the OBC platform are also planned and in progress (see success criteria A2.3).

Another key OBF project objective is to 'foster bibliodiversity by engaging more geographically distributed stakeholders'. Contributing to this work, the OBC's Year 1 targets included the organisation of 8 outreach workshops with global stakeholders. The OBC succeeded in delivering all these planned events, as well as participating in many more (a full list of events featuring contributions from the OBF project team can be found on our PubPub site). An outreach highlight in Year 1, was a 3-day workshop in Cape Town, entitled 'Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context' (see success criteria A2.5), which was co-organised by the OBC. This direct engagement with OA publishing in diverse national contexts informed the OBC's call for applications to its Collective Development Fund Grant Programme, which was launched ahead of schedule in Apr 2024 (see success criteria A2.4 and A2.10).

WP3, Opening the Future (OtF):

Opening the Future (OtF) is a new funding model for open access books, which was launched under the COPIM project and is currently adopted by two University Presses, with more presses to follow. The programme funds BPC-free open access book publishing while also broadening library collections through an affordable subscription to closed content. In Dec 2023, Kira Hopkins joined the OtF team as Scholarly Publishing Outreach Officer, enhancing the model's impact by accelerating this WP's outreach efforts (see success criteria A3.4 and A3.1). In Year 1, OtF has laid the groundwork for on-boarding new presses to its model by refining its offer and holding positive discussions with several presses in the UK, US and Africa (see success criteria A3.1). OtF has been researching and reporting on the model's future: scoping plans to embed OtF within third party processes (see success criteria A3.2), and holding regular meetings and consultations with Jisc, Lyrasis and other key stakeholders. The team are also working to improve their workflows to create a more robust and sustainable model: for example, in Year 1 of OBF they extended their social media presence with a new LinkedIn account, enhanced their website, and launched a call to establish a library advisory board (see success criteria A3.3).

WP4, Open Metadata & Dissemination (Thoth Open Metadata):

Thoth is an open metadata management and dissemination platform, and a non-profit Community Interest Company (CIC) registered in the UK and established under the COPIM project. A key objective for the OBF project is to ‘bridge the infrastructure gap’ in the OA book publishing landscape. In Year 1 of OBF, Thoth has furthered these efforts by significantly expanding the metadata services it offers small and medium sized OA publishers (see success criteria A4.3(c) for full details of these new services). These improvements were made by engaging with feedback from users (see A4.3(a) for information on stakeholder workshops with publishers). Thanks to an active outreach campaign, Thoth has grown both in revenue (see A4.1) and in its number of users (see A4.2)—surpassing both Year 1 targets in this area.

Importantly, Thoth’s growth has also involved fostering bibliodiversity in OA, and its new users have included numerous publishers working in non-anglophone contexts. Thoth’s published report on international metadata requirements further demonstrates the wider OBF team’s commitment to researching and facilitating global OA interoperability (see A4.3(b)), and contributes towards our project-wide objective of ‘supporting emerging OA books policy guidance’. Interoperability requires efforts amongst communities, and WP4 have used Year 1 to establish and codify close working relationships and service integrations with various key providers, including OPERAS, OAPEN, DOAB, Crossref, JSTOR, Project MUSE, EBSCOhost, ProQuest and OCLC, among others (see A4.3(a)). These working partnerships and connections are foundational for ‘enhancing engagement with the wider OA publishing ecosystem’ (another core objective for the OBF project).

WP5, Accessibility:

WP5 will conduct research on accessibility requirements and explore how these can be met through publishing workflows. By developing new tools, shaping technical protocols and sharing best practice, this group will support open access publishers by helping them to meet the diverse needs of their readers. Recruitment delays in Year 1 have meant that work on this WP has been delayed, although following interviews in May, a full-time lead on this work will be starting in September. Please see A5.1 and A5.2 in the table below for further details and our plan for accelerating and achieving these success criteria in Year 2.

WP6, Experimental Publishing:

Copim’s Experimental Publishing Group is researching ways to more closely align existing software, tools, technologies, work processes and infrastructures for experimental publishing with the workflows of open access book publishers. WP6’s work plays an important role in achieving central objectives for the OBF project: ‘to incubate and financially support OA initiatives’, and to ‘foster bibliodiversity’ in a way that includes the creation of multi-format and experimental book content. In Apr 2024, WP6 launched 3 funded pilot projects (see ‘Servpub – A Collective Infrastructure to Serve and Publish’, ‘Deep Maps’ and ‘Database as Book’) following a successful application and assessment process (see A 6.2), which also involved a collaboration with WP2 to inform the structure of OBC’s own grant-issuing programme. WP6 is committed to scoping and supporting experimental publishing futures, and the team held a matchmaking workshop to facilitate connections between academic researchers, publishers and platform/software providers (see A 6.1). Contributing to the project’s engagement with the wider OA publishing ecosystem, the WP also conducted outreach work to promote their Experimental Publishing Compendium, which officially launched in Dec 2023 (see A 6.3).

WP7, Archiving and Digital Preservation:

The Archiving and Digital Preservation Group are helping to ‘bridge the infrastructure gap’ in OA book publishing by developing new technical methods and workflows for effectively archiving complex digital research publications. At the end of Year 1 of the OBF project, the Thoth Archiving Network now

involves 4 repositories: meeting the project's Year 1 target for enhancing the impact of this important archiving infrastructure (see A7.1). WP7 have also used Year 1 to scope and launch a National Library Network (see A7.2). This network helps to 'support emerging OA book policy guidance' (a key objective for the project) by bringing together National Libraries from around the world at quarterly meetings. In Year 1 of the project, WP7 facilitated valuable, peer-led discussion around the requirements and challenges of archiving and preserving OA books by convening 3 meetings of the new National Libraries Network. Further work planned for Year 1 – a workshop with small/scholar-led presses and a report on the archiving challenges they face (A7.3)— has been delayed due to other success criteria requiring greater time and work than predicted, and due to a period of extended staff absence due to illness. The WP's delayed success criteria (A7.3) is in progress, and will be delivered early in Year 2 of the project.

2. A summary of how the project has delivered wider benefits beyond success criteria, or achieved outcomes not originally planned for.

Growth beyond what we had anticipated:

- Thoth (WP4) surpassed their Year 1 revenue and 25 presses were using Thoth services in Apr 2024.
- The OBC (WP2) surpassed their Year 1 target revenue by ca. 25%, and now boasts 61 supporting institutions.

Outreach & incubation work adapted to deliver wider benefits:

- Fostering collaboration between the many open networks and infrastructures supporting OA books has emerged as an increasingly important project focus. In Year 1 we convened a workshop at the OPERAS conference to facilitate mapping and networking, and in Year 2, we hope to see this work continue and be formalised as an OPERAS Special Interest Group.
- The OBC's multi-lingual call for grant applications launched in 2024: ahead of our Year 2 target (allowing for a longer application period) and in translation (ensuring global impact). Reflecting feedback from stakeholders, we plan to distribute ca. 10 smaller grants rather than the 3 originally planned.
- WP6's Call for Experimental Publishing Pilots became the second most-viewed publication on our site (3,200+ views). 50 applications were received, 22 of which fulfilled 'key criteria': demonstrating a demand for support in this area that was higher than even we predicted! A matchmaking workshop (not originally planned for) allowed us to advise and support applicants beyond the 3 successful candidates.

3. An update on the sustainability of the project post-funding

Embedding into partner workflows: scoping options that ensure post-project sustainability

In Year 1 of the project, WP3 scoped options for embedding the OtF revenue model in third party processes. As they outline in a recently published [report](#) on the subject, the WP are exploring the possibility of OtF becoming an arm of the OBC. They are also considering other options, including partnering with well-known and respected platforms aligned with their ethos. These conversations are ongoing, but constitute important first steps towards ensuring the sustainability and longevity of the OtF revenue model after project funding ends.

Developing sustainable governance structures

One of the most significant milestones for WP2 came in Dec 2023 when the OBC was officially approved by the Charity Commission of England and Wales as a [UK registered charity](#). This development underscored the OBC's commitment to remaining free from commercial interference in the long-term, and has important implications for a sustainable financial future post-funding.

Offering enhanced packages/services that attract new users and retain existing supporters

WP3 are in the process of finding and partnering with 3 new publishers interested in launching an OtF programme of their own. Scaling up the OtF programme by adding these new publishers will increase the range and size of the book collections available to paying OtF supporters, thus making the model's "offer" more attractive to current and potential subscribing library members.

Similarly, WP2 is working to increase the range of Supporter Programmes available for libraries and other institutions to subscribe to via the OBC. For most of 2023, the OBC offered Supporter Programmes from 7 publisher members, but in Feb 2024 it announced a major expansion, with the [addition of 3 University Presses](#): Leuven University Press, University of London Press and University of Westminster Press. By offering a new [University Press](#) package on its platform, the OBC is helping these presses to move towards a sustainable Diamond open access future, whilst also ensuring its own offer to supporters continues to grow. This growth is vital for the OBC's long-term future.

As part of WP4, Thoth has developed [a new website](#) which, as well as significantly improving the informativeness and usability of the website and the discovery of titles in the database, is provided as an open-source white-label website allowing small and medium-sized publishers to easily adopt a fully functional website for their OA book content. This new website model is proving attractive to collections of publishers wishing to create a collective identity and combined catalogue: enhancing the service Thoth can offer to existing and new supporters.

Growth in revenue

In our project bid we outlined annual revenue targets for Thoth and OBC, with an ultimate end-goal of both being financially self-sustaining at the end of the grant funding. Thoth surpassed its target revenue for Year 1 by over 250%. Thoth also surpassed their user target: 25 presses were using their services in Apr 2024 (their target was 15). Additionally, in Nov 2023, Thoth launched Thoth Plus: a model with two different paid subscription packages and offering publishers an extended suite of automated as well as bespoke services. The launch of this revenue stream is an important development for Thoth: the success and uptake of these paid-for services will contribute to a secure financial future for the platform. The OBC also surpassed its target revenue figure for Year 1 (by over 25%), and now has 61 subscribing institutions. These figures suggest an encouraging outlook for both Thoth and the OBC's long-term sustainability and financial independence.

4. How are we disseminating learning to the wider HE sector and others who might benefit from our insights?

This year, the OBF team has influenced and benefitted the HE sector and other stakeholders by disseminating its learning at a pivotal moment for OA-publishing: offering much-needed insight and hands-on expertise to inform and guide attitudes and responses to a rapidly changing academic and regulatory landscape. Year 1 of our project has seen two major developments in OA books policy: Jan 2024 marked the introduction of [UKRI's open access policy](#) for books, and in Mar 2024 a [consultation on an updated open access policy for REF 2029](#) was launched. Whilst these new and proposed OA policies both operate within a UK context, they are also significant for book publishing and higher education around the world. As the PALOMERA project has argued, policy makers carefully monitor the mandates and guidance issued by peers, and the [PALOMERA database](#) illustrates how approaches to OA mandates are monitored, replicated and repeated across international borders. What happens in the UK has an impact on how other nations develop their own OA policies, and the globalized workflows and networks involved in publishing and academia mean that these UK-centric decisions hold significance for the entire OA ecosystem. Accordingly, the HE sector, and other interested parties (including publishers and infrastructure providers), have responded to the UKRI and REF policies with great interest. The policy and consultation have been met with approval by many, but have also been a source of 'controversy', surprise, fear and complaint for others. OA book publishing has been placed in the spotlight!

In this context, it has been vital for the OBF project to disseminate its own learning in this field: a rich expertise developed through research conducted and experience obtained during year one of this project, but also built-up during its predecessor project, COPIM (2019-2023). This year, our project community has intervened in the active debates enlivened by the new policy announcements by offering advice on what a sustainable, community-led, equitable and bibliodiverse future for OA books might look like, how it might be supported by new OA policies and mandates, and how OA books can benefit academics and the wider public in important ways. An illustrative example of this is our project's co-authored [response to the UKRI policy update](#). This community-led report has been viewed over 500 times since it was published in January 2024. It highlights the perspective of an HE librarian and an OA publisher, whilst raising concerns and questions informed by the project team's expertise and shared commitment to 'collectively reimagining and reconfiguring the funding and circulation' of OA books. A [published response to the REF 2029 consultation](#) is scheduled for publication early in Year 2 of the project.

In the introduction to our project's UKRI policy response, the co-authors clearly state their intention to 'feed into conversations within the open research community, as well as potentially into the further refinement of funder policies'. Social media has been another important way of feeding into these conversations and disseminating our learning. For example, project team member Lucy Barnes [shared her expertise on X \(formerly Twitter\)](#) to 'myth bust' some of the criticisms of OA book publishing that circulated following the policy announcements in the UK. Via our project and team members' social media accounts, positive narratives, statistics and research on OA book publishing were disseminated, allowing us to influence the conversation on X, Mastodon and LinkedIn, where many of the informal, but most influential, debates on the merits of OA books were taking place.

Following her X myth-busting thread, Lucy Barnes was invited to publish an article in Research Professional News, in which [she disseminated her expertise](#) to a further audience – university leadership. The article offered correctives to a 'number of misconceptions deriving from a lack of familiarity with open-access book publishing', and included specific recommendations and calls to action. Several accounts shared the article on social media, including the Liverpool John Moores University Research Support account, which recommended it to their staff as a 'fantastic, well-informed

piece'. As this example illustrates, the publication of longer articles and blog posts has played an important role in disseminating our learning to the HE sector, and intervening in current OA book debates this year.

Our publications have become a source of reference and guidance to academics and institutions navigating the changing regulatory landscape. Over the course of the past year, the OBF project team and the wider 'Copim community' are often cited as an illustration of positive, equitable OA book publishing, bolstering arguments that new OA mandates need not push academics towards expensive BPC-models alone. In a journal article published in Feb 2024, in the wake of the REF implementation, Simon J. Batterbury et al cite the 'Open Book Futures project' and its OBC presses as evidence that 'costs of [book] production are no longer restricted by the need to raise BPCs from authors alone' and that 'libraries and funders' can contribute. Similarly, the project is referenced as evidence that 'there is work underway towards the development of an open infrastructure to support wider collaborative publishing' in a recent report prepared by Research Consulting, commissioned by UCL Press.

In Year 1 of the OBF project, our research has intervened at the very heart of the debates enlivened by recent OA policy announcements. Indeed, our research is cited in a WONKHE article by Dinah Birch and Steven Hill (Director of Research at Research England), in which Birch and Hill welcome consultation with the sector on the REF 2029 policy, and reference a Copim community publication as evidence that 'a diverse publishing landscape has begun to emerge, with a range of business models'. As Research England continue to communicate and consult with the sector on their proposed OA books policy, Hill has repeatedly referenced OBF and Copim, for example at well-attended public events at Liverpool and London attended by publishers, librarians and academics. A particularly valuable source has been the OBC's annual report, published in Feb 2024, which Hill valued and referenced at these events as offering evidence of what collective OA funding models can achieve.

These examples illustrate how our research is directly impacting and guiding policy on, and attitudes towards, OA book publishing within the HE sector. Moreover, our expertise and learning is also benefitting and influencing commercial publishing companies, who are also responding to increased interest and impetus in OA book publishing by launching their own OA book platforms and funding models. Our influence is evidenced by the fact that a consultant from Peter Lang contacted the project for advice, directly noting his company's admiration for the OtF revenue model pioneered by the Copim Community. Similarly, publishing behemoth De Gruyter referenced OtF on the website and in the press release announcing the launch of UPLO (their own OA eBook initiative), acknowledging that their model 'leverages insights gained' from OtF's research and expertise. The OtF model's influence can also be seen in Bloomsbury Academic's collective funding model, 'Bloomsbury Open Collections', which launched in 2023. Whilst our project team have concerns about the transparency and equitableness of some of the new, large-scale OA initiatives emerging from commercial publishing companies, it is undeniable that our research, and the dissemination of our work practices through tool kits and guides (such as our practical guide to establishing an OtF-style model), is informing and leading the approaches to developing OA revenue models used by commercial publishers. In this way, the OBF project is impacting and guiding attitudes to OA book publishing in both the HE and commercial sectors.

5. What networks and/or approaches are we currently utilising for dissemination? And are there further ways in which we plan to connect with others to share insights from our project?

Approaches utilised for dissemination

Our project uses social media to disseminate research and news, and to intervene in debates, by commenting and sharing information on open access book publishing. We have been using and growing the X (formerly [Twitter](#)) account (2000+ followers) and [Wikipedia](#) presences established under the COPIM project, whilst adding a [Mastodon](#) account (410 followers) and [LinkedIn](#) page (190 followers) in response to the way academics' and librarians' social media preferences have altered in recent months. In addition, several of our initiatives use their own websites, social media accounts and mailing lists for dissemination. For example, the OBC shares regular updates on new subscribers and project activities on their [information hub news blog](#), and then shares these, and other updates, via their [X account](#). Since the year began, the OBC have produced over 70 blog posts, sharing their progress with a network of existing supporters and members, but also to potential supporters and interested parties. The OBC uses an active social media presence and blog to demonstrate their growing success, to celebrate those who support them and to advocate for the community, growth and success that is possible with community led OA initiatives. Meanwhile, our OtF revenue model has been posting [regular updates on its News pages](#) since the start of the COPIM project, to announce new library members and new books funded. OtF also launched a newsletter for their subscribers in Year 1 of the OBF project: an important approach to dissemination that allows them to further share their model's achievements, and encourage existing supporters to renew their subscriptions.

In addition to social media, the project has utilised events such as conference presentations, posters and exhibition stands, as well as participation in webinars, seminars and other talks, to disseminate our research. Our team have participated as organisers, speakers and presenters at over 50 outreach events in Year 1 of the project, disseminating our initiatives and research to audiences both online and in-person. A full diary of our events can be found on our PubPub site [here](#). As this online diary documents, these events have presented our work to a range of audiences, and have often been enabled and enhanced by collaborations with networks. For example, our outreach efforts regularly target HE librarians, who we hope will be interested in signing up to OtF, OBC or Thoth, but who are also important potential advocates and facilitators for the sustainable, diverse, community-led and equitable future for OA book publishing that our project seeks to deliver. Many of our informational outreach events for librarians have been hosted in partnership with the organisations and bodies of which they are members. For example, in Jan 2024 the project co-organised [a webinar with SCONUL](#), during which speakers shared their perspectives on the library's role in OA book funding and publishing. Another [webinar](#) was organised with Project Muse, during which attendees were introduced to the project's OtF OA book revenue model. A [video recording](#) of this Project Muse webinar has attracted over 190 views since it was posted in Nov 2023 and the popular event garnered 400+ registrations on the day.

Wherever appropriate, the workshops organised by the project team are supplemented by report-style blog posts on our [PubPub site](#): this approach offers an opportunity to formally reflect on the event, and to share the findings and insights gained with a wider network. Examples of these posts can be found [here](#), [here](#) and [here](#). We also use our PubPub site to disseminate updates, news, and research findings with others. In the first year of OBF, we have published over 30 posts on our PubPub site, and have received over 34,000 page views from 14,5000+ unique users. We have also published our findings

in other forums: for example, Miranda Barnes, from WP7, published a [blog on the Digital Preservation Coalition website](#), highlighting the project's work on archiving and preservation. Meanwhile, [an interview with Toby Steiner](#) published on open-access-brandenburg.de highlighted the work of Thoth and the wider project in a German-language piece.

Global and multilingual approaches to dissemination

One of our key project objectives is 'to foster bibliodiversity by engaging more 'geographically distributed stakeholders'. Thus, as a project we are utilising, and continuing to develop, multilingual approaches to dissemination, which allow us to connect more directly with others around the world. For example, our new Copim community [website](#) was created with international accessibility built in by design. The site communicates key information about our project in 6 languages and this is a feature we plan to enhance and expand in future: by both improving the functionality and accuracy of the site's existing translations, and by broadening the number of languages represented. (See Simon Bowie's [blog post](#) for further details on the rationale behind the website's design.)

We have also disseminated some of our key publications in multiple languages. For example, in Apr 2024, Work Package 2 disseminated their [call for applications](#) to their Collective Development Fund Grant in English, Spanish and Portuguese. By investing in high-quality translations of the call, we hope to attract a broader pool of applicants for a grant that aims to support 'quantity, quality and diversity' in open access books. And, this approach seems to be working! Within its first 5 weeks on the site, the call was already the most viewed publication on the OBC's PubPub news blog for Year 1 of the project – having been viewed nearly 3,000 times. The Spanish and Portuguese translations are the second and third most viewed posts on the site, each with over 150 views (the majority of which represented readers in Brazil, Columbia, Bolivia and other non-Anglophone countries). The call has been picked up and highlighted by [fundsforngos.org](#) and [opportunitydesk.org](#). Once the call is closed, we plan to carefully analyse the geographical distribution of grant applications received, alongside data on the number and location of views the call received outside of the UK, so that we can enhance the geographical range of our dissemination in future calls.

In addition to disseminating multilingual calls for participation, we are also committed to sharing insights gained from our project workshops, surveys and research with a diverse, global audience. Communicating in languages other than English is particularly important when advocating for a bibliodiverse future, and when researching OA publishing in non-Anglophone contexts. Our approach here is exemplified by a [recent blog post](#) on our PubPub site which is available in Portuguese, Spanish & English. The blog shares findings from a multi-lingual project workshop in which Latin American book publishers kindly shared their needs and practices when it comes to OA book publishing. Earlier in Year 1, we were also invited to take part in a seminar series to celebrate SciELO's 25th Anniversary. SciELO is a project partner that works with publishers and librarians in Latin America. The event featured presentations from OBC, OtF and on the OBF project as a whole, simultaneously translated into Spanish and Portuguese, with the recording [on YouTube](#). We plan to host more global and multilingual of this kind in Year 2 of the project. We are hoping to connect with networks of publishers and library stakeholders in Europe, South America and Africa through workshops that will use translated slides and materials, and simultaneous translators and facilitators, as appropriate.

Crucially, the discussion and learning disseminated at these outreach events is not limited to those able to attend online or in person. As a project we endeavor to share the materials and discussion points from our workshops more widely by making slide decks and handouts available to download under a CC 4.0 licence via our project [Zenodo](#). Many of these materials gain hundreds of views, for example [this presentation](#), originally given at the Munin Conference on Repository-Led Preservation of

OA Books, has been viewed 550+ times, and [the slides](#) from our Latin American publishers workshop had already been viewed 41 times and downloaded 19 times during their first 2 days on Zenodo.

This year, we have been able to identify and reach geographically distributed stakeholders thanks to close liaison with an extended network of global partners and experts. For example, we hold regular consultancy meetings with representatives from Lyrasis in the US, and co-organised a webinar with them in Apr entitled '[Bridging Altruism to Strategy in OA Book Publishing](#)'. We have plans to support versions of this webinar in EU and UK contexts in the coming months. We have also established close working relationships with organisations working in Africa, including the University of Cape Town, the African Platform for Open Scholarship and the Association of African Universities, with whom we co-organised a workshop in Cape Town entitled '[Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context](#)'. This event included the participation of librarians and publishers from 10 different African countries. Further visits to Africa are in the works, with multiple members of the OBF project invited to participate in the Diamond OA event scheduled for Cape Town in Dec 2024, and the OtF team speaking at an online OA Workshop for the Publishers Association of South Africa in late May. Finally, we will continue to use consultancy budget to work closely with Amanda de Souza Ramalho of SciELO Books. This partnership has already helped us to forge connections with many networks and institutions in Latin America, as Amanda has helped to set up meetings, deliver presentations and translate materials. Thanks to this partnership, Thoth now have 5 Latin American publishers represented on their platform, and in year 2 of the project Thoth will expand their data model to better enable multilingual extension, for example through the provision of data fields for title and abstracts in multiple languages.

6. A case study highlighting the impact of our project

In this case study we will focus on metadata: an essential part of the OA knowledge ecosystem. The creation and dissemination of accurate, detailed and open bibliographic data is vital for making sure that open access books are discoverable and accessible to all. Thus, key objectives for the OBF project are (a) to increase knowledge of metadata best practices and policies; (b) to improve the quality and availability of metadata for OA books; and (c) to support OA publishers in creating, curating and disseminating their metadata in diverse national contexts. In Year 1 of the project, we have made considerable progress towards achieving these targets: producing a strong and positive impact on OA book publishing, and the wider HE sector, via the work of Work Package 4, [Thoth Open Metadata](#).

Thoth was founded under the COPIM project, and is now a key partner in the OBF project. It is a non-profit, open metadata management and dissemination platform, which is consciously designed for OA book metadata. Using Thoth, small and medium sized publishers can quickly generate metadata files in various formats (including MARC, ONIX, JSON and BibTeX), and these formats are also expertly tailored to meet the specifications of key platforms (including Project MUSE, OAPEN, JSTOR and Google Books).

In Year 1 of the OBF project, Thoth significantly improved and expanded the services they offer small and medium sized OA publishers, directly collecting and responding to [feedback from their users](#). First, the range and richness of metadata export files has been extended and enhanced: for example, its MARC record exports were improved after [consultation with metadata librarians](#) to include a CCO license note and authoritative subject headings. Importantly, this year also saw Thoth extend their ability to assist with the distribution and preservation of OA metadata and book content. For example, Thoth signed [partnership agreements](#) with OAPEN and Crossref that allow them to act as a vital intermediary: opening up a free and easy route for presses to create and register DOIs for their books and chapters and share their books and corresponding metadata via OAPEN's platform and the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB). Facilitating integration with OAPEN and Crossref was

highlighted as an important feature when initial research on publishers preferences was conducted, for example Jeff Pooley, from mediastudies.press, cited OAPEN as an important dissemination platform, but one that they had found required time-consuming, ‘hand crafted’ XML. Further details of the range of services added and enhancements made by Thoth this year can be found in detailed reports published here, here, here and here. Additionally, this YouTube video provides a clear and helpful walkthrough of Thoth’s new and improved website, which now includes an innovative new white-label book catalogue: a template that was developed in response to feedback and recommendations from a number of international presses.

Thoth’s impact this year is evidenced by the number of new publishers using its services. In Jul 2023 18 publishers were using Thoth, but in Apr 2024 this figure rose to 25: a larger number of users, who are also now accessing and benefitting from a wider range of services. Moreover, Thoth now boasts a more geographically diverse user base, including 3 Latin American publishers. The interest in what Thoth offers has been clear during the many outreach activities that the Work Package has participated in this year. For example, their poster “Thoth Open Metadata Management and Distribution for OA books” won a prize at Open-Access-Tage in Berlin, and has been viewed over 2,000 times, and downloaded over 300 times from Zenodo.

Thoth’s impact is significant because they are lowering the entry barrier to good metadata management. As Laura Rodríguez from Open Book Publishers (OBP) explained in Apr 2023: ‘I’m not very tech-savvy [...] Thoth can help people like me who don’t have that knowledge or background – it’s very user-friendly and you can just make the most of it’. Thanks to Thoth, small and medium sized OA publishers like OBP can quickly and easily produce, disseminate and archive high-quality metadata that meets the various specifications required by multiple distribution platforms. Importantly, they can also do that on Thoth for free! And this affordable, straightforward and time-saving solution allows smaller publishers to make their OA books discoverable and accessible to readers both in and outside the HE sector. Thoth’s is a system that ensures a more equitable and bibliodiverse research landscape: making sure that open access books, including those published by smaller presses, are not excluded from the supply chain. As Jeffrey Edmunds wrote in Nov 2023: ‘platforms like Thoth, are important initial steps toward building an infrastructure for the creation, maintenance, curation, and sharing of metadata in alignment with the principles of Open Access’.

7. Lessons learnt

The Open Book Futures (OBF) project builds directly upon the work of the COPIM project (Community-led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs). Like OBF, COPIM (2019-2023) was co-funded by Research England Development fund and Arcadia, and many of COPIM’s partners and team members are now working on OBF. We felt it would be valuable to use this section of the report to reflect on how these foundations, established under the COPIM project, have influenced and shaped Year 1 of the OBF project.

A level of continuity in both personnel and working practices has allowed the OBF project to launch quickly and effectively. For example, we were able to continue using the Mattermost platform established under COPIM, which offered a familiar way of communicating between work packages and partner organisations. The messaging platform also offered a record of previous communications, which could be searched and referenced (even by new team members) so that the knowledge and workflows established under the previous project could inform OBF’s work. Similarly, we were able to maintain a schedule of project meetings established under the previous project: without re-timetabling we could ensure monthly Senior Management Committee meetings that were open to the whole project team, and that benefitted from familiar and established expectations around reporting and participation. As

new members have joined the project, they have been inducted by COPIM ‘alumni’ and this has facilitated accelerated on-boarding and team-building. This stability in personnel, knowledge and working practices has freed up time and energy for achieving wider project objectives. For example, the deep and wide-ranging advances in Thoth’s services, and their ability to formalise and strengthen connections with other providers, were certainly facilitated by a team who were already well-used to working effectively together and with partners across the OA publishing landscape.

Our outreach work has also benefitted from OBF’s public status as a proud successor to the COPIM project. Under COPIM, the team organised and participated in over 100 international workshops, conferences and webinars, establishing a strong reputation as knowledgeable and trust-worthy advocates for open, community-led OA book publishing. The networks and contacts made under COPIM have allowed us to hit the ground running with the OBF project. Members of the team received invitations to speak, and were approached as potential co-organisers, panel participants and sources of expertise. We have also been able to develop existing social media presences established under the COPIM project, garnering and expanding upon a body of supporters and connections to expand the dissemination of our research and insights. Similarly, our project’s [PubPub site](#) now collates reports and posts created under COPIM alongside new publications created under OBF. This has created a large, rich and searchable trove of advice-sharing, updates, knowledge and reflection, which is a resource that documents over 4 years of developments in OA book publishing.

Crucial to this successful and wide-ranging dissemination has been our ability to continue using the ‘COPIM’ moniker, which has become a recognised and trusted brand name in an increasingly busy OA publishing landscape. Early in Year 1, we chose to continue referring to our network of partners and team members as the ‘Copim community’ and our project logo defines OBF as a ‘Copim community project’. For further reflection on our ability to leverage and maintain this respected brand identity, please see Lucy Barnes’s thoughtful [report on the subject](#).

Year 1 of the OBF project exemplifies the benefits in efficiency, outreach and team morale that are gained from working on a 3-year research project that follows directly on from a previous, successful project. We would argue that there are lessons to be learned here about effective allocation of project funding, and the potential advantages to be gained from supporting projects that explicitly expand upon an immediate predecessor. However, this is not to say that the transition from COPIM to OBF has been frictionless. We have had to be careful to ensure that continuity in workflow and personnel does not lead to stagnation, whereby the status quo is unquestioningly accepted, at the cost of encouraging new ideas and innovation. An example of this is perhaps provided by the OBC continuing to use Trello boards to project manage their outreach work at the start of Year 1. This system was established under COPIM, but as the project’s scope and the OBC team expanded under OBF, this original project management workflow became unfit for purpose. Moreover, the ‘free-to-use’ version of Trello was disbanded this year, forcing the team to quickly seek a new, open-source platform at a busy time for subscription renewals. This process was complicated by needing to transfer and update processes and information gathered throughout the course of COPIM, as well as Year 1 of OBF.

New team members who have joined the Copim community as part of the OBF project, have expressed concerns about needing to be mindful of respecting systems established under the COPIM project, and have acknowledged that operating in the footsteps of a very successful predecessor project may have discouraged them from questioning established workflows and/or suggesting new alternatives. We have sought to manage this by opening up discussions to all project colleagues, and engaging in early discussion with all colleagues about how they felt the project could be best be managed, always emphasising that we seek to operate with as flat an organisational hierarchy as possible. Voices old and new have a say in how the project is managed.

There have also been some delays and complexities in collating financial reporting in Year 1 of OBF. In part, this may have been because partners have been asked to adapt to slightly different

reporting workflows arising from the project's switch to a different lead institution. In some instances, this adaptation has been made slower than expected because of an expectation that things would continue as before. An over-reliance on continuity meant that processes and expectations were perhaps not clearly established and communicated from the start of OBF (as may have happened more readily and formally at the start of a brand new project).

We have learned a lot in Year 1, and are confident that we now addressed those initial blockers. Going into Year 2 we will continue to update new guideline documents for partners. We will also continue to hold induction meetings with new staff, in which we will explicitly welcome challenges and updates to existing work practices, and open up space for these discussions in our open monthly project meetings. We would be happy to pass on the lessons we have learned to other research projects in similar positions to OBF: offering our advice on how to reap the benefits, and address the challenges, involved in extending and expanding upon the foundation of an immediate, successful predecessor project.

8. Risk register

ID	Description	Original probability score	Original impact score	Current probability score	Current impact score	Mitigation required (as described in original risk register)	Mitigation taken	Outcome
1	Global financial uncertainties. Potential consequence: could have impacts on UK inflation rate and/or the Pound Sterling exchange rate for non-UK partners.	Medium	High	Medium	High	Increase frequency of payments to partners to 3-monthly to reduce risk and include upfront payment to partners.	Quarterly reporting & invoicing implemented as planned. Project Manager working with Lancaster University finance team to process reporting quickly, and initial delays have now been rectified. Several non-HEI partners now employing an accountant to assist with financial reporting, forecasting & planning. Exchange rates standardised across project: quarterly averages used based on gov.uk rates.	UK inflation rate has fallen (11% in Autumn 2022, to 3.2% in May 2024). Our total expenditure for Year 1 was within budget, with some underspend. In Year 2, project management team will continue to monitor this risk & encourage timely financial reporting & payments. We will ask the funder about budget virements to bolster travel budgets, to combat rising hotel & subsistence costs.
2	Extended staff absences due to personal contexts (e.g., looking after dependants, illness) or difficulties in attracting staff with relevant skills	Medium	High	Medium	High	(a) Draw on large already-established networks to attract shorter/longer term replacements, as required, (b) build on significant talent pool already embedded in the project, including amongst both early	Planned mitigation was followed – with team members successfully redistributing responsibilities during period of staff absence in WP7. Recruitment & line management challenges at one partner meant they could no longer host a role as planned. Mitigation taken: (a) budget allocated for the role was moved to another partner (with SMC and funder approval); (b) research work re-allocated to a role	In Year 1, WP7 was impacted by some extended staff absence due to illness. But, WP successfully delivered & exceeded two-thirds of their Year 1 targets thanks to successful mitigation. WP5 deliverables have been delayed due to difficulties in hiring staff member for associated

	Potential consequence: unforeseen delivery challenges within particular Work Packages.					and later career staff, to redistribute responsibilities across the project.	hosted by another partner; (c) when project failed to recruit to this new role at 0.5, the role was readvertised as a 1.0 and received a larger pool of candidates.	<p>research role – despite the mitigating actions taken.</p> <p>In year 2, project management team will encourage WP leads to spread work-load across multiple team members, and to practice careful documentation of decisions & workflows, so as to further mitigate impact from long-term absences.</p> <p>Where possible, new vacant roles will be advertised with flexible FTEs, to encourage more applicants. Advisory & governance boards, and extended project networks, now established, can be utilised to promote vacancies more widely.</p>
3	Unanticipated pressures on library/publisher budgets impacting on effectiveness of outreach aimed at generating financial commitments from stakeholders	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	(a) Encourage financial commitments from stakeholders by offering additional incentives (e.g. expert advice services for new supporters), (b) undertake reprioritisation of project activities, to enable the delivery	(a) WPs have offered incentives for renewal & financial commitment, e.g. OtF has worked with presses to offer subscribers perpetual access to more titles. OBC has signed a partnership with Jisc to enable libraries to subscribe directly via the Jisc Subscription Manager, for a default 3-year term. (b) extensive outreach activities conducted, often beyond those required by project deliverables. c) annual reviews prepared; reports reflecting on strategies and	In Year 1, revenue targets were met and exceeded. But, new policy mandates (e.g. UKRI OA book policy and the REF OA consultation in the UK) are putting new pressures on library budgets + increasing the number of OA initiatives seeking support.

	Potential consequence: Challenges for OBC/Thoth in meeting proposed revenue targets, with potential impacts on post-project sustainability.					of additional outreach efforts (e.g. additional workshops to promote the new services), (c) use mid-point performance evaluation to inform adaptation of outreach strategies, including assessing perceptions and effectiveness of services offered and opportunities to conduct outreach via new channels, (d) if, by the end of the project revenue targets have not been met, seek support from other funders or seek to integrate the organisations within the operations of trusted partners.	workflows written; workshops & surveys with stakeholders & users conducted.	
4	Project structure, involving many partners, in	Low	Medium	Low	Medium	(a) Use extensive experience gathered during the COPIM project,	(a) monthly SMC meetings used to measure progress on deliverables, and reprioritise / redistribute tasks as necessary. Tasks shared where	In Year 1, the project team worked well together, and project management techniques used have enabled team to successfully

	different national/cultural contexts, with different priorities, leading to collaboration challenges Potential consequence: impacts on Work Package workplans and increased project management workload.					including application of Agile project management principles, to reprioritise and, if necessary, redistribute project tasks to ensure the timely completion of all deliverables, (b) explore using different project management procedures (e.g. asynchronous meetings, new digital tools) to shift collaboration dynamics.	appropriate – collaboration and knowledge-sharing across WPs encouraged by, e.g. in-person team meeting held in Mar 2024; and active messenger & co-working platform Mattermost (b) new procedures implemented as required: reporting templates for monthly meetings; task tracking boards for outreach activity via Mattermost, etc.	deliver the majority of targeted objectives.
5	Challenges in fully incorporating the technical requirements from stakeholders in scholarly dissemination channels	Low	Medium	Low	Medium	(a) Work with policy stakeholders (e.g., Jisc, UKRI OA policy, Coalition S) to scope & include compliance criteria in Thoth & Open Book Collective development, (b) work with publisher stakeholders to	(a) Team has had regular contact with policy stakeholders – and has monitored updates on new mandates carefully. Where necessary project team has sought clarifications on how the project’s initiatives comply with / relate to new mandates, e.g. the UKRI funding limits for OA monographs. (b) Workshops held with publishers and other stakeholders to learn more about their developing needs & requirements.	In Year 1, the project has successfully navigated new updates on policy/funder mandates, and has continued to develop new services that meet technical requirements.

<p>Potential consequence: Impacts on participating publishers' ability to fully deliver compliance with policy/funder mandates (e.g., Plan S, REF-after-REF2021).</p>					<p>develop agreed development priorities, in dialogue with policy stakeholders where feasible.</p>	<p>New & expanded services being developed to target these.</p> <p>(c) Where appropriate: our outreach and promotional materials directly address details of new policy / funder mandates, to show how our current offerings can deliver compliance.</p>	
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9. Success criteria

- Total Number of Success Criteria for Monitoring Period: 24 (to be completed by May 2024)
- Total Number of Success Criteria Completed for Monitoring Period: 21 completed + 3 “in progress – delayed”

Work package	Success criteria	Success criteria description	To be completed by	Status	Actual outcome
2. OBC	(A2.1) Increase OBC revenue	(D2.1a) £250,000 revenue generated in Year 1	May-24	Completed	Success criteria exceeded by ca. 25%+.
2. OBC	<i>See above</i>	(D2.1b) At least 3 new publisher/service provider sign-ups (Year 1)	May-24	Completed	<p>3 new publishers signed-up: University of Westminster Press, Leuven University Press and University of London Press all launched on the OBC on 5 Feb 2024. See press release: “Three university presses join the Open Book Collective”. (Feb 2024). <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.3fc4b79b</p> <p>See A2.6 (a Year 2 success criteria) for details of further sign-ups already in progress.</p>
2. OBC	(A2.2) At least 2 library outreach events organised in the UK (with JISC, RLUK, SCURL) and US (with Lyrisis), promoting OBC work	(D2.2) At least 2 library outreach events completed and documented	May-24	Completed	<p>Success criteria exceeded, with multiple outreach events completed in Year 1, including:</p> <p>Library Outreach Event 1 (UK) Title: Open Access Week 2023: Open Access Books: Panel Discussion. Date: 26 Oct 2023 Location: online Participating organisations: Organised by University of Derby & University of Essex. No. of participants: 40 Recording: “Open Access Week 2023 - Open Access books: Panel discussion”. (Jan 2024). DerbyUni Library. <i>YouTube</i>. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=k4YiVSqfIRY (45+ views)</p>

Further documentation of event: Deville, J., Sanders, K., & Corazza, F. (Feb 2024). "What a difference a year makes: An update on the Open Book Collective's activities over the past 12 months". *OBC Information Hub*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.3db1e0a1>

Library Outreach Event 2 (UK)

Title: Copim Community exhibition stand, evening social event & paper presentations

Date: 8-10 Apr 2024

Location: UKSG 2024, Glasgow

Further documentation of event: See X thread for a record of Copim Community's participation:

https://x.com/Copim_community/status/1773318375239754211

Planned follow up: Tom Grady & Elaine Sykes have been invited to deliver their very successful presentation again, as a recorded webinar hosted by UKSG.

Library Outreach Event 3 (US)

Title: Open Book Collective: Collective Paths Toward an Open and Sustainable Ecosystem for Monographs

Date: 12 Dec 2023

Location: CNI conference, Washington

Participating organisations: University of California, Santa Barbara

No. of participants: 50

Recording: "Open Book Collective: Collective paths toward an open and sustainable ecosystem for monographs". (Jan 2024). CNI:

Coalition for Networked Information. *YouTube*.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=obWzE2_uNk8 (80+ views)

Further documentation of event: Deville, J., Sanders, K., & Corazza, F. (Feb 2024). "What a difference a year makes: An update on the Open Book Collective's activities over the past 12 months". *OBC Information Hub*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.3db1e0a1>

Library Outreach Event 4 (US)

					<p>Title: Presence at the Charleston Conference (in-person and online) Presentation title: A community-led future for OA books: How can new OA infrastructures enable libraries to support “scaling small” in scholarly publishing? Poster title: Closing the Knowledge Gap: Improving Open Access Knowledge Sharing between Publishers, Authors, and Libraries Date: 27 Nov 2023 (presentation); 6 Nov-1 Dec 2023 (poster) Location: Charleston Conference Participating organisations: University of California, Santa Barbara No. of participants: 88 (for online presentation) Recording: “A community-led future for OA books”. (Apr 2024). CharlestonConference. <i>YouTube</i>. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kMstZahjPus (4 views) Further documentation of event: Deville, J., Sanders, K., & Corazza, F. (Feb 2024). “What a difference a year makes: An update on the Open Book Collective’s activities over the past 12 months”. <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.3db1e0a1</p>
2. OBC	(A2.3) 2 publisher workshops (inc. 1 with OBC members) scoping requirements for OBC Information Hub (with WP3, Lyrasis & OPERAS) & CRM, multilingual interface, grant allocation pilot	(D2.3a) Multilingual platform interface (draft) and spec document for CRM	May-24	Completed	<p>WP met with software engineers (DeltaQ) in Dec 2023 and agreed a plan for development next steps, including work on CRM and other platform features. Specifications for interface enhancements have been informed by consultation with publishers, including via the workshops with publishers detailed below. Publisher workshops co-organised with Lyrasis & OPERAS planned for Year 2.</p> <p>Publisher Workshop 1 Title: OBC Information Hub and Collective Development Fund scoping workshop Date: 22 Jan 2024 Location: online Participating organisations: punctum, White Horse Press, Mattering Press, African Minds, Westminster University Press, University of London Press, Leuven University Press, DOAB/OAPEN, Thoth, OBP, meson press, mediastudies.press</p>

					<p>No. of participants: 15 Report on event: Fathallah, J., & Deville, J. (Mar 2024). "Collective Development Fund Grant Programme: Scoping update". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.f748da11</p> <p>Publisher Workshop 2 Title: Evaluating evaluation criteria for OA book publishers: An exploratory workshop Date: 18 Apr 2024 Location: Online No. of participants: 20 Further details: This workshop will help to inform the resources around evaluation criteria that will feature on the project's Information Hub. A report on the event will also be published on the project's PubPub early in Year 2 of the project.</p>
2. OBC	<i>See above</i>	(D2.3b) Interim blog post on grant allocation & management procedures	May-24	Completed	<p>Blog post on grant allocation & management procedures has been published: Fathallah, J. (Jan 2024). "First Collective Development Funding Call to Open in Apr 2024". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.495490c0</p> <p>Call for grant applications launched in Apr 2024 (ahead of schedule, see A2.10 below) and has been viewed nearly 3000 times. Spanish & Portuguese versions also published: "OBC Collective Development Fund Grant Programme: 2024 Call & Guidance". (Apr 2024) <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/obc-collective-development-fund-grant-programme-2024-call--guidance</p> <p>Grant allocation & management procedures have passed through internal feedback processes. This work has been supported in particular by the US-based non-profit Invest in Open Infrastructures, which has run a similar grant management programme. Feedback has also been sought and received from SPARC EU, who have joined the project as a consultant (via the OBC, in line with the original grant proposal).</p>

					<p>The WP also launched a scoping survey to help inform the grant allocation & management procedures. This survey was available in both English and Spanish, and closed at the end of Feb 2024: Fathallah, J. (Nov 2023). "Open Book Collective Development Fund: Scoping Survey". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.e5f289c6</p> <p>In addition, WP2 collaborated with WP6 on their parallel grant funding programme, which will award 3 grants funds to experimental publishing pilot projects: collaborating on specific grant allocation/management procedures.</p>
2. OBC	(A2.4) 1 workshop on the financial, governance, and communication challenges associated with supporting OA infrastructures in diverse contexts (with DOAB & SPARC Europe)	(D2.4) Interim blog post on OA infrastructures scoping work	May-24	Completed	<p>Blog post on OA infrastructures scoping work published: Fathallah, J., & Deville, J. (Mar 2024). "Collective Development Fund Grant Programme: Scoping Update". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.f748da11</p> <p>Workshop was held in Nov 2023 (see details below), supplemented by insights from OBC publisher members workshop (see A2.3).</p> <p>Workshop 1 Title: Workshop to inform the OBC Development Fund Grant Date: 29 Nov 2023 Location: online Participating organisations: African Platform for Open Scholarship (formerly Continental Platform), Digital, Preservation Coalition, Invest in Open Infrastructures, Knowledge Futures, OpenEdition/Language Science Press, Public Knowledge Project, SPARC EU No. of participants: 13 Report on event: Fathallah, J., & Deville, J. (Mar 2024). "Collective Development Fund Grant Programme: Scoping Update". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.f748da11</p>

2. OBC	(A2.5) 3 international workshops including in the EU (with OPERAS & SPARC EU) & rest of the world (RoW) (with the African Continental Platform and SciELO) scoping opportunities/barriers to consortial funding models	(D2.5a) New outreach targets identified in Europe and RoW	May-24	Completed	<p>New outreach targets in Europe & RoW have been identified and approached. The OBC now has 61 supporters. New supporters have included Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf; KB, National Library of the Netherlands; McMaster University Libraries; Rowan University Libraries; University of Waikato Library; and Zentralbibliothek Zürich. If permission is granted, new supporters are announced via press releases on the OBC news blog: https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/news</p> <p>Outreach work has also involved organising international workshops scoping opportunities/barriers to funding OA around the world. One workshop was held in Jul, in collaboration with SciELO (an organisation that supports OA publishing in Latin America) and a second workshop took place in Feb in Cape Town in collaboration with University of Cape Town Library/UCT Press/African Platform for Open Scholarship. A third workshop was held with Southern Women Academics Network. See workshop details below.</p> <p>International Workshop 1 Title: Open Book Futures: Working together to Build Community-owned Infrastructures for OA books to its members Date: 14 Jul 2023 Location: online Participating organisations: SciELO, Thoth, OtF No. of participants: c.60 Event page: https://25.scielo.org/en/seminars/copim/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8142775 Further documentation: Deville, J., Sanders, K., & Corazza, F. (Feb 2024). "What a difference a year makes: An update on the Open Book Collective's activities over the past 12 months". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.3db1e0a1</p> <p>International Workshop 2 Title: Open Access and Global South Scholars: Needs, Experiences,</p>
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					<p>Barriers</p> <p>Date: 11/01/2024</p> <p>Location: Online</p> <p>Participating organisations: Southern Women Academics Network</p> <p>No. of participants: 10</p> <p>Report on event: Fathallah, J. (Feb 2024). "Open Access and Global South Scholars: Needs, Experiences, Barriers. Workshop Report." <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.b423d75c</p> <p>International Workshop 3</p> <p>Title: 'Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context'</p> <p>Date: 7–9 Feb 2024</p> <p>Location: Cape Town</p> <p>Participating organisations: African Platform for Open Scholarship (formerly Continental Platform), Association of African Universities, OAPEN/DOAB, Thoth, University of Cape Town</p> <p>No. of participants: 40</p> <p>Programme & slides: Fathallah, J., & Deville, J. (Jan 2024). "Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context: Workshop Programme, Slides & Resources". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.c8fbbc53</p> <p>Report on event: Published: Fathallah, J., & Deville, J. (Mar 2024). "Reflections on 'Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context', a workshop at the University of Cape Town". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.6fa8c7df</p>
2. OBC	(A2.5) See above	(D2.5b) Interim blog post on EU/RoW library landscape scoping work	May-24	Completed	<p>Report published: Fathallah, J., & Deville, J. (Mar 2024). "Reflections on 'Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context', a workshop at the University of Cape Town". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.6fa8c7df</p>

2. OBC	(A2.6) Continue to increase OBC revenue	(D2.6a) At least 3 new publisher and service provider sign-ups (Year 2)	May-25	In progress	Applications for membership received from 4 new presses. To be announced in due course.
2. OBC	(A2.6) See above	(D2.6b) £600,000 revenue generated in Year 2	May-25	In progress	
2. OBC	(A2.7) 5 workshops (1 UK, 2 US, 1 EU, 1 RoW) for librarians (supported by Jisc, SCURL, RLUK, SPARC Europe, OPERAS)	(D2.7) 1 report on barriers to consortial funding from libraries & supporting OA infrastructures in diverse contexts	May-25	In progress	<p>Workshop 1 (ROW) The project has been invited to contribute to OA Diamond Publishing workshop/event in Cape Town in Dec 2024</p> <p>Workshop 2 (EU) Application accepted by LIBER for a pre-conference workshop</p> <p>Workshop 3 (US) Biodiversity event organised in collaboration with Lyrisis & Jisc, took place in May 2024.</p> <p>Workshop 4 (US) WP plans to organise decentralised workshops with publishers across the EU in collaboration with OPERAS SiG.</p> <p>Workshop 5 (EU) TBC</p> <p>Report on barriers to consortial funding & supporting OA in diverse contexts Forthcoming</p>
2. OBC	(A2.8) 1 new promotional online video produced	(D2.8) 1 video published	May-25	Not started	

2. OBC	(A2.9) CRM & advanced search for OBC platform finalised	(D2.9) CRM system, advanced platform search features, and a multilingual interface operational	May-25	In progress	
2. OBC	(A2.10) New call for OBC grant applications	(D2.10a) Grant allocation & management procedures published	May-25	Completed	Call published on 16 Apr 2024: "OBC Collective Development Fund Grant Programme: 2024 Call & Guidance". (Apr 2024) <i>OBC Information Hub</i> . https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/obc-collective-development-fund-grant-programme-2024-call--guidance
2. OBC	(A2.10) See above	(D2.10b) 1 OBC grant allocated, 1 new call announced	May-25	In progress	WP expects to allocate multiple grants in second half of 2024 and to announce its second call for applications.
2. OBC	(A2.11) Interim evaluation of OBC, including impact of global outreach, completed	(D2.11) Interim evaluation report published & management plan updated	May-25	Not started	
2. OBC	(A2.12) OBC Information Hub (with WP3) launched, in collaboration with Knowledge Futures (creators of PubPub, an open-source, end-to-end	(D2.12) OBC Information Hub launched	May-25	In progress	Outline plans developed at the in-person project workshop in Mar 2024. Currently scoping terms of reference.

	publishing platform for knowledge communities, which will be used to host the Information Hub).				
2. OBC	(A2.13) Further increase OBC revenue	(D2.13a) £1,000,000 revenue generated in Year 3	May-26	Not started	
2. OBC	(A2.13) See above	(D2.13b) At least 3 new publisher/service provider sign-ups (Year 3)	May-26	Not started	
2. OBC	(A2.14) 6 library outreach events (1 UK, 1 US, 3 EU, 1 RoW; supported by Jisc, SCURL, RLUK, SPARC Europe, OPERAS, African Continental Platform, SciELO)	(D2.14) 300+ libraries briefed	May-26	Not started	
2. OBC	(A2.15) Further call for OBC grant	(D2.15) 2 OBC grants allocated	May-26	Not started	

	applications announced				
2. OBC	(A2.16) Final full evaluation of OBC	(D2.16) 1 final performance evaluation report	May-26	Not started	
3. OtF	(A3.1) Direct outreach to at least 5 presses about shifting to the presses to engage with OtFRM	(D3.1) Discussions initiated with 3 presses about adopting the OtFRM	May-24	Completed	<p>A report on OtF's direct outreach work in Year 1 is available here: Hopkins, K. (Apr 2024). "Engaging with New Presses: Growing the Opening the Future Programme and Community". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/y1nzugp1</p> <p>In Q1 & Q2 of Year 1, WP liaised with the President of Assoc University Presses and OA SIG coordinated by Project MUSE for advice on preparing an attractive approach/call for participants for next presses to join OtF. Direct outreach work has accelerated following the appointment of a new Scholarly Publishing Outreach Officer in Dec 2023.</p> <p>In Q3 & Q4 of Year 1, the WP held productive discussions with presses in the US, UK and RoW.</p> <p>OtF has organised and participated in many outreach events in Year 1. A full list can be found on the project PubPub site here: https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/open-book-futures-outreach. Attendee reports indicate that these events were attended by presses and important sector stakeholders.</p> <p>In Apr 2024, a meeting with the UK Director for the Assoc University Presses (Anthony Cond) highlighted further leads to pursue in Year 2.</p>
3. OtF	(A3.2) Work with Jisc and Lyris to scope options for embedding the	(D3.2) Interim blogpost on options for embedding	May-24	Completed	<p>Blogpost on options for embedding OtF in partner workflows is published here: Hopkins, K., & 3, W. P. (Apr 2024). "How Long is a Tangled Web of String?" <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/01mst8w2</p>

	OtFRM in third party processes	OtFRM in partner workflows			Work with Jisc and Lyrisis: In Year 1, regular meetings have been held with Jisc, Project MUSE and Lyrisis. For example, meetings with Jisc & CEUP have focused on outlining how OtF might amend the renewal process for UK members; and meetings with the Jisc Sherpa Books implementation team have been an opportunity to give feedback on the beta version of their platform and to help them refine to the way they present Diamond Models (including OBP's and OtF).
3. OtF	(A3.3) 2 outreach events for publishers & libraries on OtFRM toolkits & workflows (supported by Jisc, SCURL, Lyrisis, SPARC Europe)	(D3.3) Reports via blogposts on updates on OtFRM toolkits & workflows	May-24	Completed	<p>Reports on updates to OtF toolkits and workflows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hopkins, K. (Apr 2024). "Improving Workflows and Updating Infrastructure at Opening the Future". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/t72gg6n9 • Hopkins, K., & WP3 (May 2024). "Opening the Future seeks Library Advisory Board Members". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/i9i9izvd • Grady, T. (Feb 2024). "New year update, Jan 2024". <i>Opening the Future</i>. https://www.openingthefuture.net/news/111/ • Grady, T. (Forthcoming, Summer 2024). "Getting Out From the Back of the Sofa: Sustainable Funding for Open Access Monographs Through Opening the Future and Other Collective Funding Models". <i>National Acquisitions Group</i>. • See also the various other updates posted here: https://www.openingthefuture.net/news/ <p>Outreach Workshop 1 Title: The Times They Are A' Changing: How Can We Fund Open Access Books Equitably and Sustainably Date: 1 Nov 2023 Location: Online Participating organisations: Project MUSE, CEU Press, California Digital Library No. of participants: 430+ attendees Recording: "Opening the Future Webinar: How Can We Fund Open Access Books Equitably and Sustainably". (Nov 2023) Project MUSE.</p>

					<p><i>YouTube</i>. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fqDv80x2F8Y&t=4s (198 views) Documentation of event: Hopkins, K., & 3, W. P. (Jan 2024). "The Times They Are A'Changing: How Can We Fund Open Access Books Equitably and Sustainably". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.4780fe88</p> <p>Outreach Workshop 2 Title: Getting Out From the Back of the Sofa: Sustainable Funding for Open Access Books Date: 9 Nov 2023 Location: Munin Conference, Tromsø campus of UiT The Arctic University of Norway No. of participants: 30 attendees Event page: https://site.uit.no/muninconf/program/ Abstract: https://septentrio.uit.no/index.php/SCS/article/view/7156 Documentation of event: https://zenodo.org/records/10226504</p>
3. OtF	(A3.4) Create specification and advert to recruit Outreach Coordinator	(D3.4) Outreach Coordinator position filled	May-24	Completed	Interviews for 'Scholarly Publishing Outreach Officer' were held on 17 Oct 2023, and a new colleague (Kira Hopkins) was appointed. Kira joined the team on 11 Dec 2023.
3. OtF	(A3.5) Begin transitioning revenue models of new presses to OtFRM	(D3.5) 3 new non-UK/US presses in transition	May-25	Not started	
3. OtF	(A3.6) 2 international workshops for publishers (scoping sustainability of OtFRM model)	(D3.6) 1 report with OtFRM case studies published	May-25	In progress	

	and librarians (scoping engagement strategies) (supported by SPARC Europe, OPERAS)				
3. OtF	(A3.7) OBC Information Hub (with WP2) launched	(D3.7) Publisher Info/Advice Hub update	May-25	In progress	
3. OtF	(A3.8) 5 workshops on OtFRM revenue models for presses in different countries	(D3.8) New OtFRM Presses' transition to OA documented in Publisher Info/Advice Hub	May-26	Not started	
3. OtF	(A3.9) Final full evaluation of OtFRM	(D3.9) 3 new publishers joint OtFRM programme	May-26	Not started	
4. Thoth	A4.1 Increase Thoth revenue	D4.1 £10,000 revenue generated in Year 1	May-24	Completed	Success criteria exceeded by 250%.
4. Thoth	A4.2 Increase publisher use of Thoth services	D4.2 15 publishers using Thoth services	May-24	Completed	As of Apr 2024, there are 25 publishers using the Thoth platform. Of these, 19 have metadata ready to export from the new Thoth website: https://thoth.pub/publishers Thoth has worked with & onboarded a variety of new international presses in Year 1, including Latin American SciELO Books publishers (EDUFBA, EDITUS, EDUEPB) and L'Harmattan Open Access (a Hungarian subsidiary of L'Harmattan [France]).

					<p>The new Thoth Plus services were launched on 16 Nov 2023 and the initial response has been very positive. Thoth are now working with 5 publishers (Mattering, WHP, adocs, punctum, OBP) to establish submission workflows to several platforms. A blog post discussing the new Thoth Plus services has been published on the project's PubPub site: Arias, J., Higman, R., Hillen, H., Gatti, R., van Gerven Oei, V. W. J., O'Connell, B., Ramalho, A., & Steiner, T. (2024). "Thoth Expands Team and Collaborations, Introduces New Services". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.a2e47002</p>
4. Thoth	<p>A4.3(a) 2 workshops for publishers scoping Thoth requirements services, including in non-anglophone contexts (supported by COKI, DOAB, OPERAS, PKP)</p>	<p>D4.3a Service integration landscape study published</p>	May-24	Completed	<p>Service integration landscape study published here: Steiner, T. (n.d.). "A growing network of open infrastructures: federated services with Thoth". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/growing-network-of-open-infrastructures-federated-services-with-thoth</p> <p>Publisher Workshop 1 Title: Thoth Publisher Scoping Workshop Date: 16 Nov 2023 Location: Online Participating organisations: ADOCS Verlag, Edinburgh Diamond, Lancaster University, LSE Press, Loughborough University Library, mediastudies.press, Mattering Press, meson press, Open Book Collective, Open Book Publishers, punctum books, SciELO Books, Scottish Universities Press, textem Verlag and University of Westminster Press No. of participants: 21 Report on event: Steiner, T., Arias, J., Gatti, R., Higman, R., Hillen, H., Ramalho, A., & van Gerven Oei, V. W. J. (Jan 2024). "Thoth Publishers Workshop 2023". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.0daca04e</p> <p>Publisher Workshop 2 Title: Thoth Latin American Publishers' workshop Date: 11 Apr 2024</p>

					<p>Location: online</p> <p>Participating organisations: SciELO Books, Editorial UNRN (Argentina), Editorial Flacso Ecuador, Editorial UR (Colombia) and EUNED (Costa Rica)</p> <p>Report on event: Ramalho, A., Arias, J., & Steiner, T. (May 2024). "Workshop do Thoth Latin American Publishers, abril de 2024 / Taller de editores latinoamericanos Thoth, abril de 2024 / Thoth Latin American Publishers' workshop, Apr 2024". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.1a61edad</p>
4. Thoth	A4.3(b) See above	D4.3b 1 interim blog post on int'l metadata requirements	May-24	Completed	<p>Blog post published: Steiner, T. (May 2024). "Implementing international metadata standards and requirements in Thoth: an update". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/implementing-international-metadata-standards-requirements-in-thoth</p>
4. Thoth	A4.3(c) See above	D4.3c New publisher services launched (automatic reference generation, DOI minting, book content distribution)	May-24	Completed	<p>Thoth Plus service model launched on 16 Nov 2023. A blog post discussing the new Thoth Plus services has been published on the project's PubPub site: van Gerven Oei, V. W. J., Steiner, T., Arias, J., Gatti, R., Hillen, H., Higman, R., & Ramalho, A. (2024). "Launching the Thoth Plus service model". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.0e9234b1</p> <p>For further discussion of new services, see also: Arias, J., Higman, R., Hillen, H., Gatti, R., van Gerven Oei, V. W. J., O'Connell, B., Ramalho, A., & Steiner, T. (2024). "Thoth Expands Team and Collaborations, Introduces New Services". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.a2e47002</p> <p>And Steiner, T., van Gerven Oei, V. W. J., Hillen, H., & O'Connell, B. (2024). "A growing network of open infrastructures and federated services with Thoth". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.92d1c71e</p> <p>Major website update now live: https://thoth.pub . Further information available here: Hillen, H., & Arias, J. (2024). "Launch of the new Thoth Open Metadata website". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.1e5f1d4c</p>

Video overview of features available here:

<https://youtu.be/HtD7GdPKdgg>

And changelog here: <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/blob/master/CHANGELOG.md>

Formalised collaborations have been made with various platforms, which will help to facilitate service integration & content distribution across these platforms, e.g.:

- Thoth-OAPEN collaboration agreement signed, this enables Thoth to act as an umbrella for small publishers who would have difficulty joining OAPEN on their own. (<https://oapen.org/article/8778704-oapen-and-thoth-open-metadata-sign-partnership-agreement>)
- DOAB Trusted Partner Network: Collaboration agreement in place. (<https://doabooks.org/en/article/jstor-african-platform-for-open-scholarship-apos-fulcrum-and-thoth-open-metadata-join-doab-trusted-platform-network>)
- Thoth confirmed as an official Crossref sponsor: enabling help with DOI minting for smaller publishers. (<https://thoth.pub/solutions/doi>)
- Agreement w. OCLC signed.
- In exchange with Jisc Library Hub to facilitate Thoth integration with Jisc NBK.

Other advancements in services & new services in development include:

- Improvement to MARC records in response to feedback from metadata librarians (e.g. now include a dedicated note re. their CC0 license)
- Early scoping work on OMP-Thoth plugin development begun.
- Work on full ONIX export begun (as compared to platform specific ONIX outputs that only use a subset of the full data available in Thoth).

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early stages of Traffic Light System being implemented. • Major update of Thoth book catalogue. In conjunction with this, planning a new service to offer hosting of catalogue and white-label website, which will be of particular interest to consortia and national-level catalogues. • Linked to Thoth's Crossref sponsorship, Thoth are now able to offer Crossmark and Crossref Similarity Check services.
4. Thoth	A4.4 Further increase Thoth revenue	D4.4 £25,000 revenue generated in Year 2	May-25	Completed	
4. Thoth	A4.5 Further increase publisher use of Thoth services	D4.5a 30 publishers using Thoth services	May-25	In progress	
4. Thoth	A4.5 <i>See above</i>	D4.5b At least 5 new publishers use services/features developed in year 1	May-25	In progress	
4. Thoth	A4.6 Mid-point evaluation with publishers using the service (survey)	D4.6 1 mid-point evaluation report & update to project management plan	May-25	Not started	
4. Thoth	A4.7 2 workshops to conclude research on	D4.7a 1 study of book metadata requirements in	May-25	In progress	

	international metadata requirements (supported by DOAB, OPERAS, COKI, PKP)	diverse national contexts			
4. Thoth	A4.7 See above	D4.7b New services for EU/RoW publishers and for librarians, multilingual interface	May-25	In progress	
4. Thoth	A4.8 Further increase Thoth revenue	D4.8 £65,000 revenue generated in Year 3	May-26	Not started	
4. Thoth	A4.9 Further increase publisher use of Thoth services	D4.9 45 publishers use Thoth services	May-26	Not started	
4. Thoth	A4.10 Development of new services, database features, service integrations, non-English user interfaces for Thoth finalised	D4.10 Open-Source code made available online via Github	May-26	In progress	
5. Accessibility	(A5.1) 2 workshops scoping accessibility	(D5.1) Scoping report on global accessibility barriers	May-24	In progress - delayed	Arranging these workshops and scoping the report was intended to be the work of a Post Doc Research Assistant at Jisc (0.42 FTE, planned to start in M7). However, there have been delays in recruitment due to issues with line management capacity.

	requirements and obstacles with libraries and publishers (1 UK/US/EU, 1 RoW)				<p>In Year 1 the Project Management team and WP leads have been working to resolve these delays. The scoping report work has been reassigned to a new WP1 'Accessibility and Library Engagement Manager'. Interviews for this 0.5 role took place in early 2024, but we were unable to recruit a suitable candidate. Before re-advertising the position in Apr 2024, we edited the job description to emphasise the need for experience and understanding in the field of ebook accessibility, and made the role a 1.0 FTE to (a) attract a wider and more suitable pool of applicants, and (b) to ensure that, once in post, the appointee could accelerate this work, making sure that both Year 1 & Year 2 WP5 targets will be met. At time of writing, the re-advertised position has attracted a larger pool of applicants, and interviews were held in mid-May. We plan for the chosen candidate to be in post soon.</p> <p>Once a suitable candidate is in post, we plan to accelerate the performance of the WP by drawing on further support within Lancaster University, including arranging a scoping workshop in collaboration with Dr Ann-Marie Houghton (Dean of EDI at Lancaster University) & the University's inclusive learning network. Also, we are exploring the potential for delivering publisher-focused workshops in collaboration with WP4 & WP7.</p>
5. Accessibility	(A5.2) Iterative improvement of the accessibility checker tool	(D5.2) Codebase made openly available	May-24	In progress - delayed	The Software Engineer who will be responsible for working on this accessibility development work [alongside other project development work at Thoth] has been recruited and began work in Dec 2023. Whilst waiting for input from a scoping survey (see account of recruitment delays above) the developer has focussed on accelerating service development work at Thoth. This reallocation of his time, will allow for greater resource & FTE to be dedicated to this accessibility development work in Year 2, once the WP5 workflow is established.

5. Accessibility	(A5.3) 2 knowledge-exchange workshops with publishers on accessibility standards implementation	(D5.3a) 1 interim blog post on accessibility standard implementation	May-25	Not started	
5. Accessibility	(A5.3) See above	(D5.3b) Guidance on accessibility standards implementation (online toolkit)	May-25	Not started	
5. Accessibility	(A5.4) Service/software to improve accessibility compliance released	(D5.4) 5 publishers using service tool	May-26	Not started	
5. Accessibility	(A5.5) Promote service/software via at least 1 workshop and conference presentations	(D5.5) 1 workshop & conference presentations to present and promote service/software	May-26	Not started	
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.1) 1 workshop scoping experimental publishing		May-24	Completed	Workshop took place on 15 Jan 2024 and took the form of a 'matchmaking workshop', bringing together applicants for the pilot projects with invited publishers, and platform/software providers (further details below). The work of WP6 on COPIM and OBF was also presented.

	futures with 5+ OA publishers				<p>Workshop details</p> <p>Title: Experimental Publishing Book Pilots Matchmaking Workshop Date: 15 Jan 2024, 3pm-6:45pm [GMT] Location: Online Participating organisations: authors and project teams (17 proposed pilot projects presenting), platforms (e.g. Electric Book Works, Manifold, PubPub, Scalar, Juncture) and presses (e.g. UCL, LSE, Westminster, UoL, Bristol UP, Coimbra, mediastudies.press, Open Book Publishers) No. of participants: around 40 Report/written reflections on event: Adema, J. (Mar 2024). "Matchmaking Workshop Experimental Book Publishing Pilots". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/matchmaking</p>
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.2) With WP2 develop processes to allocate funding for the WP6 pilots as part of the grant allocation pilot	(D6.2) 3 pilot projects on experimental publishing assessed through the grant allocation pilot and launched	May-24	Completed	<p>3 pilot projects on experimental publishing were launched in Apr 2024. Further details of each of the selected projects can be found in the following announcements posted on PubPub:</p> <p>Kiesewetter, R. (Apr 2024). "Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project 'Servpub – A Collective Infrastructure to Serve and Publish'". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/servpub-book-launch</p> <p>McHardy, J. (Apr 2024). "Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project 'Deep Maps: Blue Humanities'". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/launching-deep-maps</p> <p>Adema, J. (Apr 2024). "Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project 'Database as Book'". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/database-book-launch</p> <p>The call for applicants for these experimental book pilot projects closed on 22 Nov 2023: McHardy, J., Kiesewetter, R., Bowie, S., & Adema, J. (Oct 2023). "CALL FOR PROPOSALS: EXPERIMENTAL BOOK</p>

					<p>PILOT PROJECTS". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/expub-pilot-call</p> <p>The call was also accompanied by detailed additional guidance to support applicants: Adema, J. (2023). "Open Call for Experimental Publishing Pilots: Background Information to Support your Application". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/expub-pilot-faqs</p> <p>The opportunity was disseminated via a thorough outreach plan, and the call for applicants became the second most-viewed publication on the Copim PubPub site, with over 3,200 views. Thanks to the widespread promotion of the call, the work package received nearly 50 applications, and 22 of these passed an initial 'key criteria' check.</p> <p>Many of the projects that applied did not have full teams consisting of a press, an author or group of authors, and a technology provider (a requirement for submission of final proposals on 1 Feb), so the WP facilitated a matchmaking process with potential partners in the form of a workshop (see workshop described above). The WP also actively supported the proposed projects with their applications to ensure they met the eligibility criteria before full submission.</p> <p>Working together with WP2 the WP drafted assessment criteria and procedures and set up an assessment panel consisting of representatives of the WP6 team, the OBC Board of Stewards, and OBC members. Full submission of proposals was due 1 Feb and the assessment panel took place 12 Feb. 3 successful projects were selected, and subaward agreements were signed with the aid of CU and Lancaster legal teams. Successful pilots were also established on CU's finance systems to allow for them to be provided with funds.</p>
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.3) 1 outreach event to promote Experimental Publishing		May-25	In progress	<p>The Experimental Publishing Compendium was officially launched 1 Dec 2023 (after the launch of a beta version in Apr 2023). The launch was promoted with a blog post: Adema, J. (Dec 2023). "Official Launch of the Experimental Publishing Compendium". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/compendium-launch</p>

	Compendium to authors and publishers				<p>Promotion of the launch included mailing list announcements, and a festive ‘calendar’ of tweets/toots (one released every day throughout Dec). A promotional video showcasing the Compendium has also been published: Bowie, S. (2024). “A brief walkthrough of the Experimental Publishing Compendium”. <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/compendium-video</p> <p>The initial, online promotion of the Experimental Publishing Compendium has been very successful. Since the launch, WP6 have been invited to discuss the Compendium in meetings with Utrecht University Library, the Alan Turing Institute, Northumbria University Library, and at a workshop of the Multimodal Appreciation project (Berlin), and it has been shared with the proposed pilot projects for inspiration. The compendium has also been presented at the matchmaking workshop to 40 authors, presses, and technology providers. The compendium was also nominated for the DH Awards 2023: Adema, J. (Mar 2024). “The Experimental Publishing Compendium Receives a Digital Humanities Awards 2023 Nomination”. <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/dhwards</p> <p>The WP are discussing plans to do a series of events with experimental publishing platform/software providers to feedback into the compendium again. WP6 will be presenting the Compendium at a roundtable on Experimenting with Academic Knowledge Production for 4S/EASST in Amsterdam in Jul 2024.</p>
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.4) Documentation methods for pilots developed	(D6.4) Open documentation of the pilots	May-25	In progress	
6. Experimental	(A6.5) Scoping of extended Compendium	(D6.5) Extended Compendium governance	May-25	Not started	

Publishing	governance structure	structure implemented			
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.5 continued) <i>See above</i>	(D6.6) Scoping report published	May-25	Not started	
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.6) Scoping of expansion and integration of the Compendium as OBC service		May-25	Not started	[A6.6 to be documented by short blog post / report]
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.7) Pilot projects concluded	(D6.7) 3 experimental books & 1 research article	May-26	Not started	
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.8) Pilot projects fully integrated with other OBC services/tools	(D6.8) Full documentation of 3 Pilot projects	May-26	Not started	
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.9) Development and expansion of ExPub Compendium finalised	(D6.9) 1 event with authors and publishers to promote ExPub Compendium	May-26	Not started	
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.1) Increase number of repositories involved in the	(D7.1) At least 3 new UK/US repositories involved in Thoth	May-24	Completed	Thoth Archiving Network now involves 4 UK/US repositories: 1) Internet Archive – automated feed: https://archive.org/details/thoth-archiving-network 2) Loughborough University, Fig Share – automated feed: https://repository.lboro.ac.uk/Thoth_Archiving_Network

	Thoth Archiving Network	Archiving Network			<p>3) University of Cambridge, D-Space – https://thoth-arch.lib.cam.ac.uk/home</p> <p>4) Zenodo – pilot automated feed (https://sandbox.zenodo.org/communities/thoth/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest)</p> <p>Expanding this network has proved challenging: with each new repository demanding new processes, specifications and rounds of testing and reconfiguration. However, in its current form, the network now offers a secure and accessible option for OA presses seeking to archive their books for future readers.</p>
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.2) Working with existing national library networks and the Digital Preservation Coalition, identify and engage with new national library stakeholders	(D7.2) At least 5 national libraries involved in discussion about requirements for OA books archiving/preservation	May-24	Completed	<p>WP7 have founded the National Libraries Network, which currently has 6 members (Qatar National Library, Library of Congress, British Library, National Library of Scotland, National Library of the Netherlands and German National Library) who are invited to quarterly meetings. The WP is also in touch with other National Libraries who have expressed an interest in being involved, including Library and Archives Canada</p> <p>The network has been established to discuss the requirements and challenges of archiving/preserving OA books. Discussions take place during regular online meetings and asynchronously via a Teams space. Meetings were held in Sep 2023, Jan 2024 and Apr 2024.</p>
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.3) 1 workshop scoping archiving challenges of small/scholar-led presses	(D7.3) White paper/report published on archiving challenges	May-24	In progress - delayed	<p>Completion of this success criteria has been delayed due to other WP deliverables requiring greater time and resource than originally planned (see A7.1 above). Moreover, a period of extended staff absence due to illness has delayed progress further.</p> <p>Ongoing work on this success criteria will be prioritised and delivered early in Year 2 of the project. The WP plans to conduct a workshop with WP4 to reduce the demand on our publisher colleagues which will then work towards this deliverable.</p> <p>The WP have started drafts of three blogposts on archiving challenges, which will feed into a larger report.</p>

7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.4) Further increase number of UK/US repositories in the preservation network	(D7.4a) At least 5 participating repositories	May-25	In progress	
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.4) See above	(D7.4b) Inclusion of at least 2 non-UK/US presses in repository archiving networks	May-25	Not started	
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.5) Informal National Libraries' network with at least 5 members on OA books archiving established	(D7.5) Blog post on establishment of informal national libraries network	May-25	In progress	Target on track to be achieved in Year 2. 7 National Libraries already on invite list for national libraries network (the 6 as mentioned above plus the National Library of Canada who will be attending from our next meeting), and three meetings already been held. Blog post in drafts, publication to follow.
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.6) 1 workshop on archiving/preservation workflows for smaller publishers & experimental books, supported by the Digital Preservation Coalition	(D7.6) Publication of 3 reports on experimental book archiving, PhD theses and 'link rot'	May-25	Not started	

7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.7) Scoping of PhD thesis archiving/preservation practices	(D7.7) Blog post on PhD thesis scoping work	May-25	Not started	
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.8) Addressing 'link rot' challenge inc. proposal to change PDF/A standard	(D7.8) Blog post or report on proposal to change PDF/A standard and link rot challenge	May-25	Not started	
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.9) Further increase the number of UK/US repositories in the preservation network	(D7.9a) 10 participating repositories	May-26	Not started	
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.9) See above	(D7.9b) 1 report on funding, technical and administrative needs for a National Libraries archiving network	May-26	Not started	
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.10) Open Educational Resources (OER), including training materials for authors,	(D7.10) OER Training materials published	May-26	Not started	

	publishers and libraries on archiving & preservation practices around PhD theses finalised				
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.11) Recommendations for national and international policy makers finalised	(D7.11) 1 report on recommendations for national and international policy makers	May-26	Not started	
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.12) Toolkit with recommendations & software for small presses finalised	(D7.12) Toolkit for small presses published	May-26	Not started	
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.13) Research on archiving and preservation of PhD theses concluded	(D7.13) 1 report on archiving of PhD theses published	May-26	Not started	

11. Materials and open access

Details of materials and papers produced, how they have been made available for free on the internet, and statistics about their use where available.

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
23 May 2024	Blog	Janneke Adema	“Looking back at year 1 of the Open Book Futures project: Reflections from the Experimental Publishing Group”	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/obfwp6year1	31
21 May 2024	Blog	Toby Steiner	“Implementing international metadata standards and requirements in Thoth: an update”	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/implementing-international-metadata-standards-requirements-in-thoth	128
21 May 2024	Blog	Toby Steiner	“A growing network of open infrastructures: federated services with Thoth	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/growing-network-of-open-infrastructures-federated-services-with-thoth	118
14 May 2024	Blog	Hannah Hillen and Javier Arias	“Launch of the new Thoth Open Metadata website”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.1e5f1d4c	174
6 May 2024	Blog	Amanda Ramalho, Javier Arias	“Workshop do Thoth Latin American Publishers, abril de 2024 / Taller de	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.1a61edad	87

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
		and Toby Steiner	editores latinoamericanos Thoth, abril de 2024 / Thoth Latin American Publishers' workshop, Apr 2024"		
2 May	PPT	Amanda Ramalho	Gestión de Metadatos, dirigida por la Comunidad, Diseminación y Archivado con Thoth Open Metadata	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11104716	50
2 May 2024	Blog	Kira Hopkins	"Opening the Future seeks Library Board members"	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/i9i9izvd	122
30 Apr 2024	Blog	Kira Hopkins	"How Long is a Tangled Web of String?"	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/01mst8w2	103
29 Apr 2024	Blog	Kira Hopkins	"Improving Workflows and Updating Infrastructure at Opening the Future"	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/t72gg6n9	40
26 Apr 2024	Blog	Kira Hopkins	"Engaging with New Presses: Growing	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/y1nzugp1	88

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
			the Opening the Future Programme and Community”		
26 Apr 2024	Blog	Rebekka Kiesewetter	“Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project ‘Servpub – A Collective Infrastructure to Serve and Publish’”	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/servpub-book-launch	209
26 Apr 2024	Blog	Julien McHardy	“Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project ‘Deep Maps: Blue Humanities’”	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/launching-deep-maps	277
26 Apr 2024	Blog	Janneke Adema	“Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project ‘Database as Book’”	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/database-book-launch	155
23 Apr 2024	Blog	OBC	“Bridging Altruism to Strategy in OA Book Publishing Workshop”	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/workshop-bridging-altruism-to-strategy-in-oa-book-publishing	165
17 Apr 2024	Blog	Toby Steiner	“OA-Interviews: Tobias Steiner (Thoth Open Metadata) über Trends und	https://open-access-brandenburg.de/oa-interviews-tobias-steiner-thoth-open-metadata-ueber-trends-und-loesungen-fuer-open-access-buecher/	N/A

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
			Lösungen für Open Access-Bücher”		
16 Apr 2024	Blog	OBC	“OBC Collective Development Fund Grant Programme: 2024 Call & Guidance”	https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/obc-collective-development-fund-grant-programme-2024-call--guidance	2,960
9 Apr 2024	Video	Thoth Open Metadata	“Part 2: Thoth’s interface for publishers demo”	https://youtu.be/sPwynCcU_00?si=Mm0gCzy0SNBcuv9u	35
9 Apr 2024	Video	Thoth Open Metadata	“Part 1: Welcome to Thoth's new website”	https://youtu.be/HtD7GdPKdqg?si=57dIhymI5odr1dQC	45
25 Mar 2024	Blog	Simon Bowie	“A brief walkthrough of the Experimental Publishing Compendium”	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/compendium-video	137
18 Mar 2024	Blog	Judith Fathallah and Joe Deville	“Collective Development Fund Grant Programme: Scoping Update”	https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.f748da11	127
14 Mar 2024	Press release	DOAB, JSTOR, African Platform for Open Scholarship (APOS),	“JSTOR, African Platform for Open Scholarship (APOS), Fulcrum, and Thoth Open Metadata join	https://doabooks.org/en/article/jstor-african-platform-for-open-scholarship-apos-fulcrum-and-thoth-open-metadata-join-doab-trusted-platform-network	N/A

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
		Fulcrum, and Thoth Open Metadata	DOAB Trusted Platform Network”		
13 Mar 2024	Blog	Janneke Adema	“The Experimental Publishing Compendium Receives a Digital Humanities Awards 2023 Nomination”	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/dhwards	39
12 Mar 2024	Blog	Judith Fathallah and Joe Deville	“Reflections on ‘Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context’, a workshop at the University of Cape Town”	https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.6fa8c7df	88
5 Mar 2024	Blog	Kevin Sanders	“Open Book Collective now available through Jisc's Subscription Manager”	https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.3766c73d	83
4 Mar 2024	Blog	Janneke Adema	“Matchmaking Workshop Experimental Book Publishing Pilots”	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/matchmaking	51
29 Feb 2024	Blog	Joe Deville, Kevin	“What a difference a year makes: An	https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.3db1e0a1	141

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
		Sanders, and Francesca Corazza	update on the Open Book Collective's activities over the past 12 months"		
25 Feb 2024	Blog	OAPEN & Thoth	"OAPEN and Thoth Open Metadata sign partnership agreement"	https://oapen.org/article/8778704-oapen-and-thoth-open-metadata-sign-partnership-agreement	N/A
12 Feb 2024	Blog	OBC	"Open Access and Global South Scholars: Needs, Experiences, Barriers. Workshop Report."	https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.b423d75c	82
5 Feb 2024	Blog	OBC	"Three University Presses join the Open Book Collective"	https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.3fc4b79b	35
2 Feb 2024	Poster	Miranda Barnes, Toby Steiner	Transparency through community-led open infrastructure: a pathway to trust	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10608699	399
2 Feb 2024	Blog	Kira Hopkins	"Copim and SCONUL: exploring practical problems and potential strategies to fund	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.415492ea	29

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
			equitable OA book publishing”		
1 Feb 2024	Report	Tom Grady	“New Year progress update, Jan 2024”	https://www.openingthefuture.net/news/111/	N/A
1 Feb 2024	Blog	OBC	“The Open Book Collective Becomes A Registered Charity”	https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.caf1d303	16
30 Jan 2024	Blog	Judith Fathallah and Joe Deville	“Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context: Workshop Programme, Slides & Resources”	https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.c8fbbc53	83
25 Jan 2024	Blog	Janneke Adema, Lucy Barnes, Joe Deville, Judith Fathallah, Rupert Gatti, Tom Grady, Kira Hopkins, Rebekka Kiesewetter, Kevin Sanders, Toby	“Copim response to UKRI funding mechanism for Diamond open access book models”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.c70b3ff1	522

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
		Steiner, and Elaine Sykes			
22 Jan 2024	Blog	OBC	“First Collective Development Funding Call to Open in April 2024”	https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.495490c0	368
15 Jan 2024	Blog	Vincent W.J. van Gerven Oei, Toby Steiner, Javier Arias, Rupert Gatti, Hannah Hillen, Ross Higman, and Amanda Ramalho	“Launching the Thoth Plus service model”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.0e9234b1	58
15 Jan 2024	Blog	Toby Steiner, Javier Arias, Rupert Gatti, Ross Higman, Hannah Hillen, Amanda Ramalho, and Vincent W.J. van Gerven Oei	“Thoth Publishers Workshop 2023”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.0daca04e	95
15 Jan 2024	Blog	Javier Arias, Ross Higman,	“Thoth Expands Team and	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.a2e47002	151

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
		Hannah Hillen, Rupert Gatti, Vincent W.J. van Gerven Oei, Brendan O'Connell, Amanda Ramalho, and Toby Steiner	Collaborations, Introduces New Services”		
12 Jan 2024	PPT	Toby Steiner	Thoth Open Metadata: Offene, community-geleitete Infrastrukturen für Metadaten-Management, Dissemination & Archivierung von Open Access Büchern	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10497883	118
3 Jan 2024	Blog	Kira Hopkins and Work Package 3	“The Times They Are A’Changing: How Can We Fund Open Access Books Equitably and Sustainably”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.4780fe88	116
1 Dec 2023	Blog	Janneke Adema	“Official Launch of the Experimental	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/compendium-launch	280

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
			Publishing Compendium”		
30 Nov 2023	PPT	Tom Grady	Sustainable Funding for Open Access Monographs: Opening the Future and other collective funding models	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10226959	22
30 Nov 2023	PPT	Janneke Adema	Experimenting with Living Books as a Posthumanities Practice	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10225905	54
29 Nov 2023	PPT	Tom Grady	Making Open Access Book Funding Work Fairly: Opening the Future Library Membership Scheme	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10224675	71
29 Nov 2023	PPT	Joe Deville	Meet the Open Book Collective	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10224941	84
29 Nov 2023	Blog	Judith Fathallah	“Open Book Collective Development Fund: Scoping Survey”	https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.e5f289c6	155

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
17 Nov 2023	Blog	Judith Fathallah	“Call For Applications: Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context”	https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/call-for-applications-towards-sustainable-open-access-book-publishing-in-the-african-context	1,373
15 Nov 2023	PPT	Judith Fathallah	Choosing Open Access for Books: Myths and Truths Beyond the BPC	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10189396	49
14 Nov 2023	PPT	Miranda Barnes	Looking to a more equitable future: the institutional repository as digital monograph archive for the small and scholar-led press	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10123352	117
8 Nov 2023	PPT	Tom Grady	Getting out from the back of the sofa: Sustainable funding for Open Access books	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10226503	16
8 Nov 2023	PPT	Miranda Barnes, Gareth Cole, Toby Steiner	“Thoth Archiving Network: Supporting Small and Scholar-led Publishers with Repository-Led	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10089532	571

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
			Preservation of OA Books”		
2 Nov 2023	Blog	Miranda Barnes	“Working across communities to ensure an open future for books: views from Copim's Archiving & Preservation team,” <i>Digital Preservation Coalition</i>	https://www.dpconline.org/blog/wdpd/wdpd2023-barnes	N/A
2 Nov 2023	Blog	Deborah Thorpe interviews Rebekka Kieswetter and Miranda Barnes	“An interview with Rebekka Kieswetter and Miranda Barnes about preserving digital books,” <i>The River-Side</i>	https://theriverside.ucc.ie/2023/11/02/preservation-online-publications-2/	N/A
1 Nov 2023	PPT	Tom Grady	The Times They Are A' Changing: How Can We Fund Open Access Books Equitably and Sustainably	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10226380	13
30 Oct 2023	PPT	Rupert Gatti	Networks of Libraries Supporting Open Access Book Publishing	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10225438	14

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
25 Oct 2023	PPT	Toby Steiner	Community-led Metadata Management, Dissemination & Archiving with Thoth	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10039857	162
24 Oct 2023	Blog	Lucy Barnes	“Introducing Open Book Futures: A Copim Community Project”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.4dc1c0d4	388
24 Oct 2023	Blog	Livy Onalee Snyder and Kevin Sanders	“Open Access Week Interview with Kevin Sanders”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.4dc1c0d4/be5639aa	96
24 Oct 2023	Blog	Livy Onalee Snyder and Rebekka Kiesewetter	“Open Access Week Interview with Rebekka Kiesewetter”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.4dc1c0d4/4fcfedc6	47
24 Oct 2023	Blog	Livy Onalee Snyder and Claire McGann	“Open Access Week Interview with Claire McGann”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.4dc1c0d4/33feac55	42
24 Oct 2023	Blog	Livy Onalee Snyder and Ross Higman	“Open Access Week Interview with Ross Higman”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.4dc1c0d4/0cad7905	40
24 Oct 2023	Blog	Livy Onalee Snyder and	“Open Access Week Interview with Francesca Corazza”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.4dc1c0d4/6ec0dde1	31

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
		Francesca Corazza			
24 Oct 2023	Blog	Livy Onalee Snyder and Tom Grady	“Open Access Week Interview with Tom Grady”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.4dc1c0d4/e4f10646	63
24 Oct 2023	Blog	Livy Onalee Snyder and Amanda Ramalho	“Open Access Week Interview with Amanda Ramalho”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.4dc1c0d4/c3ae51a8	33
24 Oct 2023	Blog	Livy Onalee Snyder and Hannah Hillen	“Open Access Week Interview with Hannah Hillen”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.4dc1c0d4/827fbe94	53
24 Oct 2023	PPT	Joe Deville	Beyond BPCs: Towards fairer, more sustainable futures for Open Access books	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10225591	48
23 Oct 2023	PPT	Toby Steiner	Collaboration over Competition: On the role of scholar-led publishing and open access in the Humanities and Social Sciences	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10033671	85
19 Oct 2023	Blog	Janneke Adema	“Open Call for Experimental Publishing Pilots: Background	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/expub-pilot-faqs	602

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
			Information to Support your Application”		
10 Oct 2023	Blog	Tom Grady	“Three more books reach funding target to go OA through OtF at CEU Press”	https://www.openingthefuture.net/news/108/	N/A
9 Oct 2023	Report	Janneke Adema and Tobias Steiner	“Looking back at COPIM... and on to new adventures, with Open Book Futures!”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.e6dea48b	156
4 Oct 2023	PPT	Toby Steiner	Open Infrastructures for Open Access books: Community-led Metadata Management, Dissemination & Archiving with Thoth	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8406751	69
3 Oct 2023	CFP	Julien McHardy, Rebekka Kiesewetter, Simon Bowie and Janneke Adema	“CALL FOR PROPOSALS: EXPERIMENTAL BOOK PILOT PROJECTS”	https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/expub-pilot-call	3,240

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
25 Sep 2023	Report	Judith Fathallah	"Report on OBC's First Annual General Assembly of Custodians"	https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/f52p8mkk	77
15 Sep 2023	Poster	Toby Steiner	Thoth Open Metadata - a Community-led Open Metadata Management and Distribution Service for Open Access Books	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8348261	388
6 Sep 2023	PPT	Judith Fathallah	The Open Book Collective: An Infrastructure for Equity and Diversity	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8322033	53
4 Sep 2023	Blog	Tom Grady	"CEU Press publishes two more new open access books funded by Opening the Future"	https://www.openingthefuture.net/news/107/	N/A
24 Aug 2023	PPT	Lucy Barnes	A field in flux: change, challenge, and collective progress for OA books	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8280162	32
22 Aug 2023	Poster	Toby Steiner	Thoth Open Metadata	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8273947	2000

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
			Management and Distribution Service for OA Books		
17 Aug 2023	Report	Simon Bowie	“Protecting user privacy on the COPIM project”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.a7eb2e1a	116
4 Aug 2023	Notice	Francesca Corazza	“First Annual General Assembly of Custodians (AGAC)”	https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/first-annual-general-assembly-of-custodians-agac	71
3 Aug 2023	PPT	Janneke Adema	COPIM Computational Publishing Pilot - Publishing from Collections Using Linked Open Data Source and Computational Publishing Pipelines	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10226311	14
13 Jul 2023	PPT	Lucy Barnes, Tom Grady, Joe Deville, Rupert Gatti, Toby Steiner	Open Book Futures: Working together to Build Community-owned Infrastructures for OA books	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8142774	61
6 Jul 2023	PPT	Janneke Adema	Promoting Biodiversity in	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10226038	46

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
			Academic Publishing		
29 Jun 2023	PPT	Lucy Barnes	Developing equitable OA for books: Building open infrastructure	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10185273	79
27 Jun 2023	Blog	Kat Baier	“CEU Press announces forthcoming release of 3 new OA titles funded by Opening the Future”	https://www.openingthefuture.net/news/102/	N/A
21 Jun 2023	PPT	Tom Grady	“Another New Normal: How Can We Sustainably Fund Open Access Monographs - Opening the Future”	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10226653	28
2 Jun 2023	PPT	Judith Fathallah	Scaling Small: The Open Book Collective Launch and Platform	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10186300	45
31 May 2023	Report	Joe Deville	“Beyond BPCs: Reimagining and re-structuring the funding of Open Access books”	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.bd1b0402	664

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
30 May 2023	Blog	Tom Grady	“LUP release 2 more books funded by OtF”	https://www.openingthefuture.net/news/99/	N/A
12 May 2023	Report	Tom Grady	“Opening the Future at CEU Press: an update on progress”	https://www.openingthefuture.net/news/98/	N/A
12 May 2023	Blog	Miranda Barnes	Announcing COPIM's 'Good, Better, Best' Practices guide for the small monograph press	https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.a83e980b	275
9 May 2023	PPT	Rupert Gatti	Introducing Thoth: Open Metadata Manager & Distribution Service for OA Books	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10225503	10
May 2023	PPT	Joe Deville, Judith Fathallah	Open Access Infrastructures and Higher Education Futures	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10225657	24
11 Apr 2023	Blog	Lucy Barnes	“Guest post – COPIM and community-led infrastructures for open access books: where are we now	https://www.oaspa.org/news/guest-post-copim-and-community-led-infrastructures-for-open-access-books-where-are-we-now-and-whats-next/	N/A

Date	Type	Author(s)	Title	Link/DOI	Views
			and what's next?", <i>OASPA</i>		

12. Photographs

Figure 1. Members of the Open Book Futures team met for a project meeting at Manchester Art Gallery in March 2024. Other Work Package members joined online. (Back row (left to right): Janneke Adema, Toby Steiner. Middle row (left to right): Tom Grady, Kira Hopkins, Anna Hughes, Gareth Cole, Lucy Barnes, Javier Arias. Front row: Claire McGann, Judith Fathallah, Joe Deville, Simon Bowie, Vincent van Gerven Oei, Ruper Gatti.) For a full list of project team members and partners, please visit: <https://copim.pubpub.org/copim-community-who-we-are>

Figure 2. Montage of Open Book Futures outreach work. Clockwise from top: Elaine Sykes presents at UKSG 2024; Livy Snyder and the Copim poster at Charleston Conference 2023; Judith Fathallah presents at the 'Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context' workshop in Cape Town, South Africa, Feb 2024; Toby Steiner presents at the 18th Munin Conference on Scholarly Publishing; Copim promotional leaflets and Open Book Collective t-shirt; Tom Grady and Toby Steiner and the Copim community stand at LIBER 2023. For further information on these and other events, please visit: <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/open-book-futures-outreach>

